

Global Assessment of Energy Consumption in Conventional Drinking Water Treatment Plants

Josi Rahel Manyoundou ✉

College of Environmental Science and Engineering, Tongji University,
1239 Siping Road, Shanghai 200092, China;
UNEP-Tongji Institute of Environment and Sustainable Development,
1239 Siping Road, Shanghai 200092, China

Article History:

Received: 28.03.2025 Revised: 24.04.2025 Accepted: 25.04.2025 Published: 30.04.2025

Abstract

Efficiency and sustainability have been widely investigated in water supply systems. This study evaluates and reviews the energy consumption of conventional drinking water treatment processes globally. By presenting and quantifying the unit energy consumption per cubic meter of treated water across key process units such as coagulation/flocculation, sedimentation, filtration, and chemical disinfection, we provide insights into historical trends, operational benchmarks, and opportunities for energy efficiency improvements. The review combines data from international case studies, peer-reviewed journal papers and technical reports from 2000–2024. Our findings confirm that conventional systems are energy efficient compared to advanced processes while also highlighting auxiliary energy demands (e.g., pumping) that offer the potential for further optimisation. Finally, the paper discusses prospects for integrating renewable energy sources, particularly solar power, to enhance sustainability. The insights form a solid foundation for optimising existing systems and guiding future investments in water treatment infrastructure.

Keywords: *Drinking Water Treatment, Energy Consumption, Conventional Processes, Coagulation, Flocculation, Filtration, Disinfection.*

Suggested citation: Manyoundou, J.R. (2025). Global Assessment of Energy Consumption in Conventional Drinking Water Treatment Plants. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 3(3), 129-140. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3\(3\).12](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3(3).12)

Introduction

Access to safe drinking water has been the centre of many initiatives in developing and developed countries alike, with expenditure in the construction of water infrastructure receiving much attention. This has been the case because the availability of safe drinking water is a fundamental requirement for public health and sustainable development (Emenike et al., 2017; Paraschiv et al., 2023). According to the World Health Organization (WHO), about 2.2 billion

people do not have access to safe drinking water, 70% of the global population is expected to face severe water shortage crises by 2050 (WHO, 2019; Zgambo, & Munthali, 2025). In addition, 1.1 billion people worldwide lack access to water (Paraschiv et al., 2023). This has been compounded by the urbanisation, with 64% of the developing world and 86% of the developed water expected to be urbanised by the year 2050 (Gehrke et al., 2015; Hamawand, 2023). Developed nations allocate substantial resources to provide access to potable water for the entire

populations, but developing countries have challenges in meeting the water requirements of their residents, particularly amid rapid population growth and urbanisation (Yongsi, 2010). In addition to this being as a result of the inherent lack of resources, water resources and infrastructure, this is also a result of the energy consumption associated with the energy-intensive water treatment plant processes (Maziotis & Molinos-Senante, 2024; Sorrell, 2015). Conventional water treatment plants (WTPs) predominantly rely on physical and chemical processes, such as coagulation, flocculation, sedimentation, filtration, and disinfection, to remove particulate matter and pathogens from raw water (Chew et al., 2016; Pakharuddin et al., 2021; Preethika & Arachchige). Notwithstanding the increasing use of advanced treatment technologies (e.g., membrane filtration, reverse osmosis) in regions with rigorous water quality standards, traditional treatment continues to be the foundation of water delivery systems in several locations globally, especially in developing countries.

In recent decades, there has been a gradual shift in water quality regulations and consumer expectations, prompting many utilities to enhance their treatment processes. However, while this has been a welcome development in some aspects, it has also led to an increase in the overall energy intensity of water treatment with 7% of worldwide electricity being consumed for the production and distribution of drinking water and for treating wastewater (Plappally & Lienhard V, 2012). These advanced technologies provide superior contaminant removal, unfortunately they are significantly more energy intensive than conventional methods (Chew et al., 2016). In contrast, conventional treatment processes, though simpler, maintain lower energy demands, making them particularly attractive in developing regions where cost and energy resources are limiting factors.

Given the importance of WTPs, in essence the importance of water itself, the objective of this study is to evaluate the specific energy consumption (kWh/m^3) of conventional treatment processes, analyse historical trends, and identify potential efficiency improvements. By synthesizing data on energy use for key

process units, we aim to provide both a benchmark for current practices and a foundation for further research into energy conservation strategies.

This study also significantly contributes to the literature, as there are no specific studies that highlight energy consumption by conventional drinking water treatment plants processes. Such work has since been concentrated on the urban water supply system.

Materials and Methods

Data Collection

The data for this research was obtained from several sources to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the situation. This included published case studies, peer-reviewed articles, technical reports and white papers, and historical operational performance records of conventional WTPs. A review of international case studies provided insights into both typical and exceptional energy performance metrics. The data from peer-reviewed articles was used to validate energy consumption benchmarks and technological advancements in equipment efficiency. These studies offered real-world data from plants operating under diverse conditions. The study also obtained data from technical reports and white papers from governmental agencies, water utilities, and industry organisations documenting process energy consumption, process flow diagrams, and performance records.

This study employed a structured and systematic approach to ensure the selection of high-quality and relevant research articles addressing the intersection of renewable energy technologies and wastewater management. The methodological framework was designed to rigorously filter the literature, use specific inclusion and exclusion criteria at each stage to refine the selection and ensure that the final dataset was directly relevant to the study purpose.

Articles published mainly between 2010 and 2015 were included in the literature search. The first search produced 17,800 results using a combination of key search terms, including "drinking water treatment", "energy

consumption” and conventional treatment processes,”.

This thorough data collection procedure, defined by rigorous screening, strict inclusion criteria, and a multi-source aggregation method, produced a strong and complete dataset. This dataset encompasses the variety of operational methods and performance metrics used in conventional water treatment plants while ensuring that the ensuing study includes both historical patterns and modern technological innovations. The overall selection of premium sources establishes a robust empirical basis for analysing energy consumption patterns and evaluating the prospective advantages of incorporating renewable energy technology into traditional treatment methods.

The selected time frame (2010–2024) was chosen to capture both historical trends and the impact of technological advancements in treatment processes and energy management.

Process Units Evaluated

The study examines conventional treatment processes, specifically:

Coagulation and Flocculation: This stage involves rapid mixing to ensure the coagulants (e.g., aluminum or iron-based compounds) are uniformly dispersed, destabilizing suspended particles and encouraging the formation of larger flocs that can settle in subsequent processes (Abd Nasier & Abdulrazzaq, 2021; Preethika & Arachchige). The energy required is primarily due to the operation of high-speed mixers.

Sedimentation and Filtration: This follows the flocculation process in which the water undergoes sedimentation where gravity aids in settling the flocs (Chew et al., 2016; Preethika & Arachchige). Then we have filtration, commonly using sand or granular media, to remove remaining particulate matter. Energy use in these steps is low due to the reliance on gravity; however, energy is still required for recirculating pumps and periodic backwashing of filters. Basically, the proposed uses gravity to settle flocs and a filtration unit (often sand or granular media) to remove residual suspended solids.

Chemical Disinfection: This stage typically employs chlorine or chloramine dosing to inactivate pathogenic microorganisms (Abd Nasier & Abdulrazzaq, 2021; Chew et al., 2016). The energy associated with this process is regarded minimal due to the associated minimal energy demand of the low-power dosing pumps (Chew et al., 2016).

Each process unit is evaluated in terms of its contribution to the overall energy consumption (kWh per m³ of treated water).

Analysis Approach

The analysis was conducted in several stages:

Standardization: Energy consumption data from different sources were normalized to kilowatt-hours per cubic meter (kWh/m³) to facilitate direct comparisons.

Trend Analysis: Historical data were examined to identify trends over time. Graphs and charts were used to visualize changes in energy efficiency for each process unit.

Benchmarking: Data were aggregated to establish baseline energy consumption values for each conventional process unit. Comparisons were then made with energy use in advanced treatment processes to provide context.

Integration of Renewable Energy Discussion: Although the primary focus is on conventional processes, the study includes a section on the integration of renewable energy, particularly solar power, to understand its potential to further reduce the overall energy footprint.

Energy consumption values for each process unit were standardised to kilowatt-hours per cubic meter (kWh/m³) and then aggregated. Historical data trends were analysed to observe:

- Variations in energy consumption over time.
- Impacts of technological improvements (e.g., more efficient mixers, optimized pump systems).
- Regional differences in energy use driven by operational practices and water quality demands.

Graphical tools, including tables, charts, and trend lines, were used to illustrate the comparisons. These visuals help in identifying patterns and deviations from the established benchmarks.

The methodology enabled a comprehensive evaluation of both current practices and

historical trends, providing valuable insights for utilities and policymakers.

Results

Energy Consumption per Process Unit

The conventional drinking water treatment plant was found to encompass the processes shown in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1. Schematic of a Conventional Drinking Water Treatment Plant

Source: Ang et al., 2015; Bukhary et al., 2020

The typical energy consumption values observed from different articles for conventional water

treatment processes have been aggregated and presented in **Table 1** below.

Table 1. Typical Energy Consumption of Conventional Water Treatment Process Units

Process Unit	Energy Consumption (kWh/m ³)	Comments /Trends
Coagulation & Flocculation	0.4 – 0.7 0.03 0.0005	Rapid mixing and flocculation add ~0.1 kWh/m ³ ; can reach 0.15–0.2 kWh/m ³ for turbid surface waters requiring intensive mixing Rapid mixing energy; modern mixers and optimized dosing have slightly reduced energy requirements over time.(Grzegorzec et al., 2023; Skoczko, 2025)
Sedimentation & Filtration	~0.1	Gravity sedimentation consumes minimal energy; filtration energy is primarily for recirculating and cleaning pumps(Skoczko, 2025).
Disinfection	0.01 – 0.03	Minimal energy use; mainly involves chemical dosing with low-power pumps(Plappally & Lienhard V, 2012).

Plappally & Lienhard (2012) also compile energy consumptions of unit processes in the US, depicting lower and higher ranges for different processes. These are detailed in Figure 2 below.

The study also obtained energy used for the disinfection processes, and these are presented in Table 3.

Figure 2. Energy Consumption of Unit Processes in Surface Water Treatment Plants in United States

Source: Plappally & Lienhard V, 2012

Table 3. Energy Consumption of Disinfection Processes in a Conventional Surface Water Treatment Plant

Disinfection process	Energy range (kW h/m ³)	Reference
Surface water chlorination/de-chlorination	$2 \times 10^{-5} - 5 \times 10^{-4}$	(Grzegorzec et al., 2023; Tejera et al., 2019)
Ground water chlorination/de-chlorination	0.002	(Bukhary et al., 2020)
General UV irradiation process	0.01–0.05; 0.0170.025	(Anis et al., 2019)
Ozone	0.03–0.1; 0.03–0.15	(Plappally & Lienhard V, 2012)
Hydranautics ultrafiltration membrane (HydraCAP 60)	0.025; 0.07–0.1	(Plappally & Lienhard V, 2012)
Microfiltration	0.18	(Pakharuddin et al., 2021; Plappally & Lienhard V, 2012)

Average historical trends in energy consumption have been presented in **Figure 3** below.

Figure 3. Historical Trends in Energy Consumption for Conventional DWTP Processes Type

Source: Maziotis & Molinos-Senante, 2024

Historical Trends, Benchmarking and Comparison

Coagulation and Flocculation: Data indicate that while early systems required energy values closer to the upper range (0.15–0.2 kWh/m³), modern systems with advanced mixing technology have achieved reductions toward the lower end of the range (0.05–0.1 kWh/m³). This improvement is primarily due to optimized impeller designs and enhanced process control.

Figure 4 below gives a comparison of electricity consumed and the cost of water treatment systems.

Figure 4. Electricity Consumed and Cost for Water Treatment System

Source: Serrenho, Norman, & Allwood, 2016

Sedimentation and Filtration: Energy consumption in these processes has shown little change over the years because they rely on gravity. However, modern filter designs and automated backwash systems have contributed to more consistent performance with energy usage of around 0.1 kWh/m³.

Chemical Disinfection: Due to its reliance on chemical dosing rather than mechanical processes, disinfection energy consumption has remained consistently low, with only marginal fluctuations due to improvements in pump efficiency.

Over the past two decades, the total energy consumption for conventional water treatment processes has typically ranged between 0.16 to 0.33 kWh/m³. Although individual process unit demands have remained largely consistent, overall improvements have been achieved through:

- **Technological Upgrades:** Enhanced mixer designs and optimized pump operations have contributed to energy savings.
- **Process Optimization:** Real-time monitoring and control systems enable operators to adjust treatment parameters more efficiently.

- **Infrastructure Enhancements:** Integration of variable frequency drives (VFDs) in pump systems has improved energy management (Molinos-Senante & Maziotis, 2022).

These improvements are modest compared to the significant energy reductions seen in advanced treatment systems, yet they are crucial for regions where conventional processes still dominate.

Benchmarking Against Advanced Processes:

When compared with advanced water treatment processes, such as membrane filtration and reverse osmosis, conventional processes require substantially less energy. While conventional processes typically consume 0.16 to 0.33 kWh/m³, advanced treatments can require multiple times that amount, particularly in seawater desalination where energy use may exceed 3 kWh/m³. These benchmarks help underscore the cost-effectiveness of conventional treatment methods in suitable applications.

Visual Representations

In addition to tables and figures presented, Figure 6 has been used to illustrate the energy consumption data:

Figure 6. Energy Consumption by the Drinking Water Treatment Processes
Source: Yatch et al., 2025

We also obtained data that compare energy consumption across the different treatment units in different types of systems, such as

desalination vs conventional drinking water vs wastewater treatment across different regions.

Figure 7. Regional ratios of the energetic toll of desalination, wastewater treatment and conventional drinking water treatment in 2015, shown as percentage of: A) total regional primary energy consumption; and B) total regional electricity consumption. Panels (C) and (D) show the regional energy consumption per capita and per United States Dollar (USD) of Gross Domestic Product (GDP), respectively. Subregions: EAP = East Asia and Pacific; EECA = Eastern Europe and Central Asia; LAC = Latin America and Caribbean; MENA = Middle East and North Africa; NAM = North America; SAS = Southern Asia; SSA = Sub-Saharan Africa; WE = Western Europe
Source: Magni et al., 2025

These show the trend of energy consumption over time for each process unit and break down the proportion of total energy consumption contributed by each process in an average DWTP.

Such visualizations not only make the data more accessible but also highlight where efficiency improvements have been most significant.

Discussion

Operational Implications

The inherent low energy consumption of conventional treatment processes underscores their cost-effectiveness, particularly in rural or economically constrained regions. In these systems, energy usage is largely confined to primary process units, namely coagulation/flocculation, sedimentation/filtration, and chemical disinfection, resulting in overall operational costs that are significantly lower than those incurred by advanced treatment systems. For example, conventional DWTPs typically exhibit energy demands between 0.16 and 0.33 kWh/m³ for core treatment processes (Skoczko, 2025). However, auxiliary components such as water intake pumping, booster pumps, and distribution networks frequently account for a disproportionate share of the total energy budget (Newman et al., 2014). Booster pumps, in particular, have been identified as major energy consumers, with values reaching as high as 150.6 Wh/m³. This suggests that further optimization of these ancillary systems—through improved pump efficiencies, variable frequency drives, and optimized scheduling—could yield substantial reductions in overall energy consumption.

Operational data also reveal that process modifications, such as the incorporation of CO₂ to enhance pollutant absorption, can reduce energy use in the conventional treatment stages by up to 40%, despite an associated increase in chemical consumption (Bhojwani et al., 2019; Yateh et al., 2025). Seasonal fluctuations add another layer of complexity; for instance, periods of elevated turbidity during the summer months lead to increased chemical dosing and intensive pumping operations (Bhojwani et al., 2019;

Bukhary et al., 2020). Such seasonal peaks, often driven by changes in source water quality and increased water demand for cooling and recreational uses, further impact the energy profile of DWTPs (Molinos-Senante & Maziotis, 2022). In summary, while conventional drinking water treatment processes are inherently efficient in energy use, significant energy savings may still be realized by addressing the energy consumption associated with auxiliary operations and by adapting operational strategies to seasonal variations. Optimization in these areas could further enhance overall plant efficiency.

Comparative Analysis with Advanced Processes, Wastewater and Desalination

When compared with advanced treatment technologies such as membrane filtration and reverse osmosis, conventional water treatment processes consistently exhibit a lower energy footprint (Grzegorzec et al., 2023). Advanced systems are engineered to remove dissolved solids, emerging contaminants, and trace pollutants, which necessitates the use of high-pressure pumps, sophisticated control systems, and multiple stages of treatment. Consequently, the energy requirements for advanced processes can be two to three times greater than those for conventional systems (Grzegorzec et al., 2023; Yusuf et al., 2020). This energy intensity not only increases operational costs but also elevates the carbon footprint of the treatment facility.

In many scenarios, especially where raw water quality is relatively high, the incremental benefits offered by advanced processes do not justify the significantly higher energy and capital costs (Ang et al., 2015; Young, 2014). In contrast, conventional processes provide an efficient and cost-effective solution that adequately meets water quality standards with a simpler operational profile. Moreover, the lower energy demands translate directly into reduced greenhouse gas emissions, a critical consideration in the context of global climate change mitigation efforts. The comparative advantage of conventional processes is further highlighted in regions where energy resources are limited or where utility budgets are

constrained, reinforcing their continued relevance in global water treatment practices.

Integration of Renewable Energy

Integrating renewable energy sources into conventional DWTPs presents a promising strategy for further reducing operational energy consumption and enhancing overall sustainability (Maziotis et al., 2023; "Using Solar and Wind Energy for Water Treatment in the Southwest,"). Solar photovoltaic (PV) systems, in particular, have emerged as a viable option due to the substantial decrease in module costs and the improved efficiency of modern PV technologies ("Using Solar and Wind Energy for Water Treatment in the Southwest,"). Empirical studies from regions such as the Middle East and North Africa have demonstrated that solar PV integration can offset between 15% and 25% of a plant's energy demand. This hybrid approach not only reduces dependence on conventional grid power—often derived from fossil fuels—but also contributes to a significant reduction in greenhouse gas emissions.

In addition to utility-scale implementations, off-grid solar-powered systems have proven effective in remote or underdeveloped areas where grid connectivity is unreliable or absent (Jones & Olsson, 2017; Olsson, 2019). These systems typically incorporate battery storage solutions to manage intermittency, ensuring a stable water supply even during periods of low solar insolation (Olsson, 2019). The economic feasibility of these solutions is further enhanced by the declining levelized cost of solar-generated electricity, making solar integration increasingly competitive with traditional energy sources (Jones & Olsson, 2017). However, the current dataset remains limited in terms of long-term performance and economic analyses of such hybrid systems. Future research should therefore aim to quantify these benefits more comprehensively, examining factors such as system scalability, integration challenges, and lifecycle cost savings.

Future Directions

The present analysis identifies several directions for more study and operational enhancement:

Energy Recovery Systems: The development and integration of energy recovery systems that harvest energy from backwash water, hydraulic losses, and other process streams should be the focus of future research. This field's emerging technologies have the potential to greatly lower net energy usage, increasing DWTPs' overall efficiency.

Innovations in Process Control: Adoption of real-time monitoring systems may dynamically optimise operational parameters when combined with machine learning and sophisticated process control algorithms. Innovations of this kind would enable treatment procedures to adapt to variations in water quality and demand, resulting in more effective energy utilisation. Specifically, adaptive management techniques might lessen energy usage peaks during certain seasons.

Hybrid Energy Models: To evaluate the long-term advantages of combining renewable energy sources, such as solar photovoltaics and battery storage, with traditional treatment procedures, thorough feasibility studies are required. In order to ascertain the overall advantages and possible drawbacks of such hybrid systems, these studies must include thorough economic analysis, environmental impact assessments, and lifespan assessments.

Regional Adaptations: Future research should prioritise the development of region-specific optimisation solutions because to the variations in climate, water quality, and economic constraints across different regions. For energy-efficient solutions to be scaled internationally, customised strategies that take local variables into account will be essential. More in-depth regional analysis and benchmarking initiatives would also be supported by the creation of extensive, publicly accessible worldwide datasets on DWTP energy usage and operating performance.

More comprehensive and systematic collection efforts are urgently needed to solve the present constraints in data availability and granularity. Deeper understanding of the effects of process changes and technology breakthroughs on energy performance will be possible through longitudinal studies that monitor energy use and

operational effectiveness over long stretches of time.

These future directions have the potential to greatly reduce operating expenses and improve the sustainability of water treatment methods around the globe.

Conclusion

The primary purpose of this study is to evaluate the energy consumption in conventional drinking water treatment processes. The study has demonstrated that conventional drinking water treatment processes continue to exhibit high energy efficiency, with core treatment units, coagulation/flocculation, sedimentation/filtration, and disinfection, typically operating within the range of 0.16 to 0.33 kWh/m³. Over the past two to three decades, despite increasing treatment demands, incremental advancements in mixer technology, pump systems, and process control have significantly contributed to maintaining or even slightly reducing the overall energy footprint of these systems. The robustness, simplicity, and cost-effectiveness of conventional treatment processes make them particularly valuable in regions where both energy expenses and water quality constraints are critical considerations.

However, the analysis has also revealed that auxiliary energy consumption, particularly for pumping raw water intake and distribution, remains a significant portion of total energy use. This indicates that while the core conventional treatment processes are efficient, there is substantial potential for further optimization in the pumping infrastructure. Addressing these auxiliary demands could yield considerable energy savings and further reduce operational costs of the water supply system.

Moreover, the growing integration of renewable energy sources, especially solar photovoltaic systems, offers promising avenues for mitigating the environmental and economic impacts associated with conventional water treatment plants and water distribution in general. Hybrid systems that combine these conventional treatment methods with renewable energy have the potential to not only lower greenhouse gas emissions but also to enhance overall

sustainability of the treatment plant. As solar technology continues to improve and become more cost competitive, its application in water treatment operations is expected to play a crucial role in transitioning toward a low-carbon water supply infrastructure and uninterrupted water supply, improving the provision of public health.

Considering findings in this study, future research should concentrate on developing robust hybrid energy models, advancing energy recovery technologies, and implementing state-of-the-art process control systems for the water treatment plants as well as water distribution systems. Such innovations are essential for further enhancing the operational efficiency of DWTPs, reducing operating costs, and meeting the growing global demand for safe, affordable, and sustainable drinking water as envisaged by the UN and WHO. Collectively, the insights from this study provide a strong foundation for optimizing existing systems and guiding future investments in water treatment infrastructure, aligning with broader environmental and regulatory objectives for organisations world over.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- Abd Nasier, M., & Abdulrazzaq, K. A. (2021). Conventional water treatment plant, principles, and important factors influence on the efficiency. *Design Engineering*, 16009-16027.
- Ang, W. L., Mohammad, A. W., Hilal, N., & Leo, C. P. (2015). A review on the applicability of integrated/hybrid membrane processes in water treatment and desalination plants. *Desalination*, 363, 2-18. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2014.03.008>
- Anis, S. F., Hashaikh, R., & Hilal, N. (2019). Reverse osmosis pretreatment technologies and future trends: A comprehensive review. *Desalination*, 452, 159-195. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2018.11.006>
- Bhojwani, S., Topolski, K., Mukherjee, R., Sengupta, D., & El-Halwagi, M. M. (2019).

- Technology review and data analysis for cost assessment of water treatment systems. *Science of the Total Environment*, 651, 2749-2761. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.09.363>
- Bukhary, S., Batista, J., & Ahmad, S. (2020). An Analysis of Energy Consumption and the Use of Renewables for a Small Drinking Water Treatment Plant. *Water*, 12(1), 28. <https://www.mdpi.com/2073-4441/12/1/28>
- Chew, C. M., Aroua, M. K., Hussain, M. A., & Ismail, W. M. Z. W. (2016). Evaluation of ultrafiltration and conventional water treatment systems for sustainable development: an industrial scale case study. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 112, 3152-3163. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2015.10.037>
- Emenike, C. P., Tenebe, I. T., Omole, D. O., Ngene, B. U., Oniemayin, B. I., Maxwell, O., & Onoka, B. I. (2017). Accessing safe drinking water in sub-Saharan Africa: Issues and challenges in South-West Nigeria. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 30, 263-272. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2017.01.005>
- Gehrke, I., Geiser, A., & Somborn-Schulz, A. (2015). Innovations in nanotechnology for water treatment. *Nanotechnology, Science and Applications*, 8(null), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.2147/NSA.S43773>
- Grzegorzek, M., Wartalska, K., & Kaźmierczak, B. (2023). Review of water treatment methods with a focus on energy consumption. *International Communications in Heat and Mass Transfer*, 143, 106674. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.icheatmasstransfer.2023.106674>
- Hamawand, I. (2023). Energy Consumption in Water/Wastewater Treatment Industry—Optimisation Potentials. *Energies*, 16(5), 2433. <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/16/5/2433>
- Jones, L. E., & Olsson, G. (2017). Solar photovoltaic and wind energy providing water. *Global Challenges*, 1(5), 1600022.
- Magni, M., Jones, E. R., Bierkens, M. F. P., & van Vliet, M. T. H. (2025). Global energy consumption of water treatment technologies. *Water Research*, 277, 123245. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2025.123245>
- Maziotis, A., Mocholi-Arce, M., Sala-Garrido, R., & Molinos-Senante, M. (2023). Energy efficiency of drinking water treatment plants: A methodological approach for its ranking. *Science of the Total Environment*, 862, 160840. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.160840>
- Maziotis, A., & Molinos-Senante, M. (2024). Understanding energy performance in drinking water treatment plants using the efficiency analysis tree approach. *npj Clean Water*, 7(1), 13. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41545-024-00307-8>
- Molinos-Senante, M., & Maziotis, A. (2022). Influence of environmental variables on the energy efficiency of drinking water treatment plants. *Science of the Total Environment*, 833, 155246. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.155246>
- Newman, J. P., Dandy, G. C., & Maier, H. R. (2014). Multiobjective optimization of cluster-scale urban water systems investigating alternative water sources and level of decentralization. *Water Resources Research*, 50(10), 7915-7938. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/2013WR015233>
- Olsson, G. (2019). *Clean Water Using Solar and Wind: Outside the Power Grid*. IWA Publishing. <http://iwaponline.com/ebooks/book-pdf/520710/wio9781780409443.pdf>
- Pakharuddin, N. H., Fazly, M. N., Ahmad Sukari, S. H., Tho, K., & Zamri, W. F. H. (2021). Water treatment process using conventional and advanced methods: A comparative study of Malaysia and selected countries. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 880(1), 012017. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/880/1/012017>
- Paraschiv, S., Paraschiv, L. S., & Serban, A. (2023). An overview of energy intensity of

drinking water production and wastewater treatment. *Energy Reports*, 9, 118-123. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2023.08.074>

Plappally, A. K., & Lienhard V, J. H. (2012). Energy requirements for water production, treatment, end use, reclamation, and disposal. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 16(7), 4818-4848. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2012.05.022>

Preethika, D. D. P., & Arachchige, U. S. P. R. Drinking water treatment plant process optimization : A case study of Kalu river basin, Sri Lanka.

Serrenho, A. C., Norman, J. B., & Allwood, J. M. (2016). The impact of reducing car weight on global emissions: The future fleet in Great Britain. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 132, 117–129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2015.02.057>

Skoczko, I. (2025). Energy Efficiency Analysis of Water Treatment Plants: Current Status and Future Trends. *Energies*, 18(5), 1086. <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/18/5/1086>

Sorrell, S. (2015). Reducing energy demand: A review of issues, challenges and approaches. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 47, 74-82. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.03.002>

Tejera, J., Miranda, R., Hermosilla, D., Urra, I., Negro, C., & Blanco, Á. (2019). Treatment of a Mature Landfill Leachate: Comparison between Homogeneous and Heterogeneous Photo-Fenton with Different Pretreatments. *Water*, 11(9), 1849. <https://www.mdpi.com/2073-4441/11/9/1849>

Using Solar and Wind Energy for Water Treatment in the Southwest. In *World Environmental and Water Resources Congress 2019*

(pp. 410-416). <https://doi.org/doi:10.1061/9780784482346.041>

WHO. (2019). *1 in 3 people globally do not have access to safe drinking water – UNICEF, WHO*. <https://www.who.int/news/item/18-06-2019-1-in-3-people-globally-do-not-have-access-to-safe-drinking-water-unicef-who>

Yatch, M., Li, C., Li, F., Gu, C., Ma, S., Lu, B., & Tang, Y. (2025). Understanding the influence of energy and chemical use on water treatment plants carbon emissions accounting. *Journal of Water Process Engineering*, 69, 106669. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2024.106669>

Yongsi, H. B. (2010). Suffering for water, suffering from water: access to drinking-water and associated health risks in Cameroon. *J Health Popul Nutr*, 28(5), 424-435. <https://doi.org/10.3329/jhpn.v28i5.6150>

Young, R. A., & Loomis, J.B. (2014). *Determining the Economic Value of Water: Concepts and Methods* (2nd ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203784112>

Yusuf, A., Sodiq, A., Giwa, A., Eke, J., Pikuda, O., De Luca, G., Di Salvo, J. L., & Chakraborty, S. (2020). A review of emerging trends in membrane science and technology for sustainable water treatment. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 266, 121867. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.121867>

Zgambo, C.P., & Munthali, R.M. (2025). Water-Energy Nexus: A Review of Technological Innovations for Resource Efficiency in Urban Water Systems in Malawi. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 3(1), 227-242. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3\(1\).22](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3(1).22)